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June 11-13, 2004

Convener

S. S. PATHAK

DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRONICS AND ELECTRICAL COMMUNICATION
ENGINEERING INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY
KHARAGPUR-721 302, INDIA

DPN-04

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on
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Department of

Electronics and Electrical Communication

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Engineering

Indian Institute of Technology
Kharagpur - 721 302, India

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INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, KHARAGPUR

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INTRODUCTION TO ALGORITHMS IN THE PHOENIX COMPUTING MODEL, SUPPORTING DYNAMIC JOINING/LEAVING OF RESOURCES.

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ABSTRACT

semantics

This paper gives an introduction to the Phoenix programming model and writing parallel or distributed application on the same which supports dynamic joining and leaving of resources. The dynamic joining and leaving is made possible through a large number of virtual node name space. The application works in similar way as in established message passing, however the communication between nodes is through messages whose destinations are specified by virtual node names rather than names bound to a physical resource. The phoenix API described here explains the for writing dynamic parallel/distributed algorithms under the model and shows how the model allows transparent migration of application states between the nodes which results in dynamic joining/leaving of the

resources. The **paper** also shows **example application level programs written** under the **phoenix model** which demonstrates **that the model is close to regular message passing models, but supporting dynamism** which makes the **application much** robust under a **dynamic** environment. **The model thus finds itself quite useful** in providing a **dynamic platform for** emerging **parallel** applications by **allowing the resources to be much** more flexible.

Keywords:

Virtual

programming.

node,

migration, distributed

1. INTRODUCTION. Parallel programming traditionally used to be associated with solving a single task across multiple processors is expanding its horizons to incorporate resources distributed across the world, thus placing distributed and parallel

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2computing in one platform. Increasingly, **clusters are being used as parallel machines, often** called **network of workstations (NOWs)**. A major influence on **the work of clusters** has been the rise of popular **public** domain software, **such** as Condor and PVM that allow **users** to farm jobs over a collection of **machines or to run a parallel program on a number of machines** connected by an arbitrary local area **network or even wide area network. Thus the trend is making many applications have a dual character of parallel as well as distributed. Parallel** because **they require a single programming interface and coordination between them thus acting as a pseudo tightly bound unit, on the other hand occasional failures and dynamic leaving/joining of resources** give them a **distributed** character. The

example applications on which these **are generally put to use are information retrieval system** e.g., web **crawlers and indexers** that cooperatively **gather and** index web **pages** without duplication, **and many internet** scale **projects involving** large number of computing **resources**. These applications now generally implemented on top of primitive programming models **such as the socket**, however **the** increasing complexity and volume of **the** application **demands a simpler** programming model than **the** existing ones. **The proposed phoenix model** has the potential **to solve** complexities described **and is** can be put to **use** for emerging robust applications. **The Phoenix model has** some specific **characteristics as** described below:

are

The proposed model is quite similar to present message passing models and hence **the parallel code** which exists for the fixed resource message passing models **can** be put to use for the model with support for dynamic resources. The semantics are designed in such a way that **the application level states** can be migrated

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166

400 DPN' 04, IIT Kharagpur, June 11-13, 2004

then the messages destined to that application, this is the basic reason in being node are queues up until a physical able to support dynamic joining/leaving of the node is not lost. The messages to that

resources.

The network configuration demands of the TTU, to model are quite flexible thus allowing LANS or

by then

multiple LANS to be connected without O DIV node, then the messages are received bothering inconsistencies

of network

configuration between them. With a little information about the configuration, the runtime environment automatically connects the participating nodes together and does not assume connection between every pair of nodes.

3. THE PHOENIX MODEL

3.1 Basic concepts

The phoenix model provides the application with a set of name spaces (0.....k) where unlike the regular message passing models the 'k' can be much larger **than** the number of participating nodes. This node name space is identifies from the application programmer point of view the destination for a message. The **actual** physical nodes has the responsibility of assuming a set of

this *virtual node* name *space*, obviously less than 'k' and the **message** destined for the set of the assuming virtual **nodes** by that specific processor is received by the processor. The mapping between the actual physical node name **space** and the set of virtual nodes is done at **runtime** by functions described in the following sections. This runtime environment combined with the ability to provide a large **virtual** name space is the reason in being able to provide the system the flexibility of dynamic resources. This runtime environment **also** allows the change of **the** number of the participating nodes even **as** the programmer is viewing a simple node name space. The choice of **the** number of the virtual node name space i.e. 'k' is entirely dependant on the need of the application. This in turn decides the mapping between **the** virtual to physical nodes.

3.2 The disjoint cover property

The participating nodes **have the** property that they cooperatively cover all the available virtual **node** name space for the system, however they are bound to follow two restrictions, known as the disjoint cover property.

The subset of the virtual nodes that the physical node assumes should be disjoint in nature.

If due to dynamic leaving of resources, at a point of time no physical node assume a virtual node, then one physical must invariably assume the unassumed node. However if at any point of time no physical nodes assume a virtual node,

This restrictions imposes a property that enables each of the all the virtual address spaces to be assumed by one and only one physical node.

3.3 The Phoenix semantics

After the basic task of specifying the number of virtual node name space has been specified the application should start sending and receiving messages through the send and receive functions described below.

```
● ph_send(ph_vp_tv, ph_msg_tm);
```

In this function **the** `ph_vp_t` is a single virtual

node name type and `ph_msg_t` is a message type. It sends a message 'm' to a physical node which is currently assuming the virtual node 'v'.

```
ph_msg_tm=ph_recv()
```

The function for receiving the message is invoked by a physical node and the function returns the message 'm' to this caller physical node which has assumed the virtual node to which the message 'm' had been sent.

The next set of semantics describes the node mapping functions which form much of the basic structure for the model. The node mapping as stated before is done by the runtime system through the assume function and release functions by the physical nodes. The semantics for these functions are.

```
ph_assume(ph_vps_t s);
```

Here the `ph_vps_t` is a number of virtual node type. The physical node which calls the assume function during runtime is allotted a set of virtual nodes which the physical node assumes ('s').

```
ph_release(ph_vps_t s);
```

The release function works in the opposite way as when the physical node calls the release function, the virtual nodes which were till then assumed by the node are released. During this time when the virtual node has not been assumed by any physical node, then the messages to the nodes are queued up. However, following the *disjoint cover property* this state can't last long as to cover up the entire virtual node name space, any node has to finally arrive which in turn assumes these set of virtual nodes.

The Phoenix model is highly dependant on the underlying communication layer for the support. The detailed analysis of the problems and implementations are out of the scope of the present paper. However the semantics of the functions which provides the application programmer an interface

through which it can
communication through the
communication layer is described below.

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Where Eve

at JAP Sy

Agarwal, Piyush, 132 Ahmed, Tauseef, 221 Anand, Abhishek,

186 Bandyopadhyay, SS, 77

Bansal, Vidit, 186 Barai, Bikash, 67

Basu, Anupam, 201, 206

Basu, TK, 221 Bellur, Praveen, 111

Bhagyaveni, MA, 123

Bhattacharya, AK, 111

Bhattacharya, Debayan, 181

Biswas, PK, 11

Biswas, Utpal, 77, 92 Chadha, Devi,

128 Chakraborti, Saswat, 111 Chandra,

Vinod, 128, 191, 196
Chattopadhyay, A, 201
Chattopadhyay, Matangini, 28
Chattopadhyay, Samiran, 18, 28
Chaubey, VK, 82 Christainson, B,
53 Das, Abhik, 11, 170 Das, Surid K,
206 Das Choudhury, P, 53 De,
Arijit, 11, 170 Dhar, Atreyee, 181
Dhir, Debendra K, 118
Dolui, S, 77
Dutta, Kinshuk, 166
Ghose, Rishik, 97
Ghosh, SK, 201
Gore, MM, 72 Goswami, P, 201
Gupta, DK, 97
Gupta, LK, 72,
Gupta, OP, 156
Hatkar, SS, 44
Jain, Rimjhim, 176
Jeevan, VKJ, 211 Kar,
Satrajit, 97 Katiyar, Vinay
K, 1, 48 Khare, Vivek, 132
Kumar, Rajeev, 38, 106
Kumar, Shishir, 137
Madhukarrao, BS, 147
Maheshwari, Preeti, 196
Malcolm, JA, 53
Meenakshi, M, 87, 101
Mondal, Sabyasachi, 11, 170

Author Index

Mudawal, Dhual, 161
Mukhopadhyay, Anirban, 92
Naskar, MK, 92 **Nath**, Aditi A, 147
Negi, TT, 6, **33** Pant, Durgesh,
137 Parashar, Surabhi, 63 Patil,
Hemant A, 221 Patil, Vasant, 38 Paul,
S, 77
Paul Choudhury, J, 23
Rajakumar, RV, 211 Rakshit,
Sharmishta, 28 Ramamurthy,
Garimella, 132 **Roy** Choudhury,
U, 97 Roy, Uttak K, 18 Sahu,
Sandeep, 216 Sajnani, Pankaj,
191 Samaddar, Sourik, 161
Saminadan, V, 87, 101 Sarkar,
Atri, 166 Sarkar, Dipankar, 67
Sarkar, Subhasree, 28
Sen, Soumya, **82**
Shankhdhar, Ankur, **137**
Shanmugavel, S, 123
Sharma, HD, 147
Sharma, Neha, 128
Singh, AK, **33**
Singh, Derminder, 156
Singh, JK, **92**
Sirisha, BS, 211
Sontakke, TR, 44
Sridhar, J, 142
Srinivas, R, 48
Srivastava, PK, 216
Suma, B, 1
Tiwari, RK, 63
Tiwari, Sudarshan, 57, 142
Tripathi, B, 132
Tripathy, AK, 6, **33**
Turuk, AK, 106.
Upadhyay, PC, **57**
Vadivel, A, 206

Venkatalakshmi, B, 123
Venkateswarlu, K, 57 Vikas,
R, 82

Chaubey, VK, 82 Christainson,
B, 53

Sami

Sark:

Sark

Das, Abhik, 11, 170

Sark:

Das, Surid K, 206

Sen,

Das Choudhury, P, 53

Shan

De, Arijit, 11, 170

Shan

Dhar, Atreyee, 181

Shari

Dhir, Debendra K, 118

Sharr

Dolui, S, 77

Singh

Dutta, Kinshuk, 166

Singh

Ghose, Rishik, 97

Singh

Ghosh, SK, 201

Sirish

Gore, MM, 72	Sonta
Goswami, P, 201	Sridh
Gupta, DK, 97	Sriniv
Gupta, LK, 72,	Sriva
Gupta, OP, 156	
Hatkar, SS, 44	
Jain, Rimjhim, 176	Suma
	Tiwar
	Tiwar
Jeevan, VKJ, 211	
	Tripat
Kar, Satrajit, 97	
	Tripat
Katiyar, Vinay K, 1, 48	
	Turuk
Khare, Vivek, 132	
	Upadh
Kumar, Rajeev, 38, 106	

Kumar, Shishir, **137**

Vadiv

Madhukarrao, BS, 147

Venka

Maheshwari, **Preeti**, 196

Venka

Malcolm, JA, **53**

Vikas,

Meenakshi, M, 87, 101

Mondal, Sabyasachi, 11, 170